

Fig. 2: Triple structure consisting of subject-predicate-object, here an example for a literary work ("Candide") from the MiMoTextBase: <http://data.mimotext.uni-trier.de/wiki/Item:Q1022>.

The SPARQL query language is composed of several building blocks: *pattern matching* (filtering of the dataset), *solution modifier* (processing of intermediate results) & *output* (output as table or graph; Arenas et al. 2010: 282). SPARQL allows users to identify new patterns in the data by recombining data sets and to formulate hypothesis-driven queries. The strengths of this query language, along with the structuring of knowledge using RDF triples, will be demonstrated through application examples during the workshop.

SPARQL queries are often issued within a single knowledge graph. However, it is also possible to query across multiple knowledge graphs, so-called federated queries (Prud'hommeaux / Buil-Aranda 2013). Here, the full potential of Linked Open Data becomes evident, as multiple datasets can be intelligently combined and insights can be gained from the combination of multiple graphs. Furthermore, redundancies between the different graphs can be avoided through these links, because in the sense of Linked Open Data, the collected knowledge of other graphs can be accessed. In the workshop, federated queries with Wikidata will be introduced and it will be shown to what extent benefits can be derived from these links.

Workshop concept

The workshop covers basic knowledge and possibilities offered by the Linked Open Data paradigm. The multilingual knowledge graph MiMoTextBase on the domain of 18th century French literature created in the project as well as Wikidata will serve as illustrative examples.

Learning Goals

The workshop aims to provide practical knowledge: How to write SPARQL queries? How to combine more than one knowledge base? What benefit can a knowledge graph offer regarding questions of literary history in particular and the humanities in general?

In the half-day workshop, the multilingual knowledge graph MiMoTextBase (Hinzmann et al. 2022a) of the project "Mining and Modeling Text" is introduced and usage scenarios are presented and visualized. In addition, participants will learn the basics of the query language SPARQL and formulate their own queries.

Specific learning objectives are the acquisition of basic knowledge about Semantic Web and RDF, Linked Open Data, Wikidata

Graph; deeper knowledge about SPARQL and the ability to formulate own SPARQL queries; familiarization with the software Wikibase and exploration of the visualization possibilities.

Fig. 3: Federated queries in SPARQL allow to query several knowledge graphs simultaneously. Example: <https://tinyurl.com/28x5ajjy>.

Target audience and requirements

The workshop is directed at digital humanities scholars with an interest in Linked Open Data and SPARQL. No special prior knowledge is necessary. Participants need a laptop and an internet connection.

Structure

The workshop consists of consecutive sessions, each of which combines input phases and practicing phases. A detailed tutorial page will be made available on GitHub Pages in advance. The participants (and all other interested parties) will be given access to it and it can also be useful in the follow-up for in-depth study (Hinzmann et al. 2022b).

The workshop itself will focus on three blocks in which the formulation of SPARQL queries will be practiced in an alternation of short impulses and more detailed hands-on sessions (for details see the schedule in the appendix). The three sections each have a different focus and are based on each other. In this way, even participants with no previous knowledge are gradually introduced to increasingly complex queries. The level of difficulty also progresses within the individual blocks, so that the focus will be on the individual writing and adaptation of sample queries and the clarification of all questions that arise in the process.

1. The first part focuses on queries about literary works. With regard to SPARQL, the central principles (such as writing simple triple patterns and possibilities of combining several triple patterns into increasingly complex queries) are dealt with here first. The benefit of such combination possibilities becomes particularly clear with the focus on the domain of the French Enlightenment novel given by the MiMoTextBase.

2. In the second part, we focus on Wikidata as the largest public knowledge graph, which can also be understood as a hub (Neubert 2017), and on authors as entities. Authors are relevant in all disciplines of the humanities and are an important hinge between different knowledge graphs. Related to the SPARQL syntax, we go a step further and integrate functions like OPTIONAL and FILTER

to extend the range of query possibilities. A start is made here with queries to authors of the MiMoText domain. In the next step, the participants can explore the data of other person entities that are of interest to them in Wikidata.

3. The third part links the previous two parts on several levels. The focus is on 'federated queries', where we will concentrate on queries that span MiMoTextBase and Wikidata. The more detailed look at authors and literary works will be continued and deepened here. In this concluding part, the importance of standards and shared data models (ontologies or 'entity schemata') as well as the linking of resources will become particularly clear.³ All authors within the MiMoTextBase, for which there are also Wikidata items, are linked to them via the property "exact match", which provides additional information and opens up various query options.⁴ The Wikibase infrastructure also offers various exploration and visualization options, which are introduced as examples (marker clusters for geo-data, timelines for birth dates, etc.).

In the concluding discussion, we want to open a space for a critical perspective on developments in the area of the Semantic Web, for example, the question of which monopolization forces and market forces have an influence (van Hooland / Verborgh 2014: 247-48; Singhal 2012). Finally, the most important application possibilities and questions will be summarized and further resources (DuCharme 2013; Lincoln 2015; van Hooland / Verborgh 2014; Blaney 2017) as well as possibilities for cooperation will be addressed.

Appendix

Workshop organization

Maximum number of participants: 25. We need a room with WiFi and a projector. We would like to offer a hybrid scenario if that is possible.

Workshop procedure (4h)

10 min. 20 min.	Welcome (introduction possibly via mentimeter) Introduction: input on Semantic Web, RDF, Linked Open Data for literary history using the Mining and Modeling Text project as an example. Wikidata & Wikibase Ecosystem, Multilingual Graph.
20 min.	SPARQL Part 1 (MiMoTextBase): (a) Input on SPARQL basics (interactive phase), SPARQL syntax, data visualization possibilities in Wikibase.
35 min.	(b) Practical part: Adapting existing and formulating simple, own SPARQL queries on the MiMoTextBase (breakout session or group work).
(15 min.)	Break
20 min.	SPARQL Part 2 (Wikidata): (a) Input: More advanced elements of SPARQL syntax such as GROUP BY and FILTER; data model for authors on Wikidata.
35 min.	(b) Practice: formulating slightly more complex queries on Wikidata.
(15 min.)	Break
20 min.	SPARQL Part 3 (Federated Queries): (a) Input: Advanced SPARQL queries: federated queries, defining prefixes, marker clusters and co.
35 min.	(b) Practice: Using federated queries and Co.
15 min.	Concluding discussion and recommending further resources

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Contributors

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- Tinghui Duan (duan@uni-trier.de; Trier Center for Digital Humanities), research interests: Computational Literary Studies and Computational Linguistics.
- Maria Hinzmann (hinzmannm@uni-trier.de; Trier Center for Digital Humanities | History Department / Digital Humanities; University of Wuppertal), research interests: Digital Literary and Cultural Studies, Linked Open Data.
- Anne Klee (klee@uni-trier.de; Trier Center for Digital Humanities), research interests: Digital Text Processing; Digital Lexicography.
- Johanna Konstanciak (konstanciak@uni-trier.de; Trier Center for Digital Humanities), research interests: Digital Text Processing; XML/Web-Technologies.
- Julia Röttgermann (roettger@uni-trier.de; Trier Center for Digital Humanities), research interests: French literature, Linked Open Data, Text mining.
- Christof Schöch (schoech@uni-trier.de; Trier Center for Digital Humanities), research interests: Computational Literary Studies.

Notes

1. Some current examples of research projects that use Wikibase: Enslaved (Zhou et al. 2020), ArtBase (Rhizome 2021), Fact Grid (Simons 2022; cf. Brunner 2022).
2. For an introduction to knowledge graphs see Hogan et al. 2021.
3. This linkage corresponds to the 5th star in Berners-Lee's (2006) Linked Open Data model.
4. Cf. the corresponding query on the MiMoTextBase: <https://tinyurl.com/2cg2nhuq>.

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